

Trigonometric interval-valued neutrosophic set setting with reciprocal fractional function using a finite weighted method

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Abstract. This paper presents a new method for creating a trigonometric interval-valued neutrosophic set via reciprocal fractional function. This article will cover the concepts of geometric, generalized weighted averaging, trigonometric interval-valued neutrosophic reciprocal fractional weighted averaging, and generalized weighted geometric. We used an aggregating model to get the weighted average and geometric. To further examine a number of sets with important qualities, the algebraic techniques listed below will be applied.

Keywords: weighted averaging, weighted geometric, generalized weighted averaging, generalized weighted geometric.

1. Introduction

Many theories have been proposed to explain uncertainty, such as fuzzy sets (FS) [1], which have a membership degree s (MD) between zero and one. For $\hat{b}, \vec{b} \in [0, 1]$ produced an intuitionistic FS (IFS) where each element has two MDs: $0 \leq \hat{b} + \vec{b} \leq 1$ and positive \hat{b} and negative \vec{b} by [2] Atanassov. Yager [3] established the Pythagorean FSs (PFS) concept, which is marked by its MD and non-MD (NMD) with $\hat{b} + \vec{b} \geq 1$ to $\hat{b}^2 + \vec{b}^2 \leq 1$. Numerous studies have examined the use of IFSs and PFSs in various fields. Their information-transmission capabilities are currently restricted. Consequently, the experts were still having trouble interpreting the data in these sets and the associated data. Wang et al. investigated the concept of interval-valued IFS with DOMBI prioritized AOs and its application for trustworthy green

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supplier selection [4]. Cuong et al. [5] claim that the three primary ideas of the picture FS are positive MD (\hat{b}), neutral MD (\check{b}), and negative MD (\vec{b}). In comparison to PFS and IFS, it offers additional benefits. Since $\hat{b}, \check{b}, \text{ and } \vec{b} \in [0, 1]$, it has been noted that the picture FS is an enhancement of the IFS that may handle greater inconsistency and $0 \leq \hat{b} + \check{b} + \vec{b} \leq 1$. Depending on the image FS description, expert opinions like "yes," "abstain," "no," and "refusal" will be supplied. The SFS for certain AOs was defined by Shahzaib et al. [6] using MADM. With SFS, $0 \leq \hat{b}^2 + \check{b}^2 + \vec{b}^2 \leq 1$ is required rather than $0 \leq \hat{b} + \check{b} + \vec{b} \leq 1$. In the beginning, Hussain et al. [7] proposed the concept of an intelligent decision support system for SFS. SFSs and their applications in DM were initially introduced by Rafiq et al. [8]. For instance, a DM problem with a property is $\hat{b}^2 + \vec{b}^2 \geq 1$.

On the condition that $0 \leq \hat{b}^3 + \vec{b}^3 \leq 1$, Fermatean FS (FFS) was first proposed by Senapati et al. [9] in 2019. Generalized orthopair FSs were initially proposed by Yager [10]. In the q -rung orthogonal pair FS (q -ROFS), both the MD and the NMD have power q ; nonetheless, their total always cannot exceed one. Palanikumar et al. [11] introduced the MADM approach for Pythagorean neutrosophic normal interval-valued fuzzy AOs. Xu et al. used IFSs to produce geometric operators, such as weighted, ordered weighted, and hybrid operators [12]. Li and colleagues [13] proposed the use of generalized ordered weighted averaging operators (GOWs) in 2002. The computation of ordered weighted distances using AOs and distance measurements was described by Zeng et al. [14]. Peng et al. studied a basic PFS based on the characteristics of AOs [15]. Dombi AOs were developed by Spherical Fuzzy Ashraf and associates [16]. Additional details on SFSs and T-SFSs are given by Ullah et al. [17, 18]. The idea of interval-valued NSSs was covered by Ibraheem et al. [19] employing a variety of AOs. Type-I extension Diophantine IVNS is discussed by Al-Husban et al. [20]. Palanikumar et al. [21–23] examined a variety of algebraic structures and aggregation approaches with potential applications.

2. AOs based on IVTNRFN

Throughout the section $\alpha = 1$. We use IVTNRFFWA, IVTNRFFWG, GIVTNRFFWA, and GIVTNRFFWG to describe the AOs. The fractional part of \angle , where \angle is a real number, may be expressed as follows if \mathcal{M} is a fractional part function: $\mathcal{M}[\angle] = \lfloor \angle \rfloor = \angle - \lfloor \angle \rfloor$. Alternatively, the difference between a real number and its largest integer value [which is determined via the greatest integer function] can be defined as a fractional part function. If \angle is an integer, then the fractional component of $\angle = 0$. Suppose that $\mathcal{M}[\angle] = \frac{1}{Z}$ is a reciprocal fractional part function. As is well known, whenever \angle is an integer, its fractional part equals 0. Therefore, \angle must not be an integer in order for $\mathcal{M}[\angle] = \frac{1}{Z}$ to be defined. With the

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exception of integers, all real numbers comprise the domain of $\mathcal{M}[\angle] = \frac{1}{\angle}$. We present the concept IVTNRFN and its operations were established and $\tan \pi/2 = \angle$

Definition 2.1. The IVNRFS $\mathbb{S} = \left[\partial, \left\langle \left[\left[\angle Z^{tl}[\partial], \angle Z^{tu}[\partial] \right], \left[\angle Z^{il}[\partial], \angle Z^{iu}[\partial] \right], \left[\angle Z^{fl}[\partial], \angle Z^{fu}[\partial] \right] \right] \right\rangle \middle| \partial \in U \right]$, where $\angle Z^{tu}, \angle Z^{iu}, \angle Z^{fu} : U \rightarrow [0, 1]$ denote the MD, IMD and NMD of $\partial \in U$ to \mathbb{S} , respectively and $0 \leq \left[\left[\angle Z^{tu}[\partial] \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} + \left[\left[\angle Z^{iu}[\partial] \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} + \left[\left[\angle Z^{fu}[\partial] \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \leq 1$.

For convenience, $\mathbb{S} = \left\langle \left[\angle Z^{tl}, \angle Z^{tu} \right], \left[\angle Z^{il}, \angle Z^{iu} \right], \left[\angle Z^{fl}, \angle Z^{fu} \right] \right\rangle$ is represent a IVTNRFN.

Definition 2.2. Let $\mathbb{S} = \left\langle \left[\left[\angle Z^{tl}, \angle Z^{tu} \right], \left[\angle Z^{il}, \angle Z^{iu} \right], \left[\angle Z^{fl}, \angle Z^{fu} \right] \right] \right\rangle$

$\mathbb{S}_1 = \left\langle \left[\left[\angle Z_1^{tl}, \angle Z_1^{tu} \right], \left[\angle Z_1^{il}, \angle Z_1^{iu} \right], \left[\angle Z_1^{fl}, \angle Z_1^{fu} \right] \right] \right\rangle$

and $\mathbb{S}_2 = \left\langle \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{tl}, \angle Z_2^{tu} \right], \left[\angle Z_2^{il}, \angle Z_2^{iu} \right], \left[\angle Z_2^{fl}, \angle Z_2^{fu} \right] \right] \right\rangle$ be any three IVTNRFNs. Then

$$(1) \mathbb{S}_1 \Delta \mathbb{S}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\frac{\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} + \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}{-\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \cdot \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}}, \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\frac{\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} + \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}{-\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \cdot \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}}, \\ \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\frac{\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} + \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}{-\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \cdot \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}}, \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\frac{\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} + \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}{-\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \cdot \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}}, \\ \left[\left[\angle Z_1^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \cdot \left[\left[\angle Z_1^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$(2) \mathbb{S}_1 \odot \mathbb{S}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \left[\left[\angle Z_1^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}, \left[\left[\angle Z_1^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}, \\ \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\frac{\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} + \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}{-\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \cdot \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}}, \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\frac{\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} + \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}{-\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \cdot \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}}, \\ \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\frac{\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} + \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}{-\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \cdot \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}}, \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\frac{\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} + \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}{-\left[\left[\angle Z_1^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \cdot \left[\left[\angle Z_2^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}}}} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(3) \varrho, \mathbb{S} = \begin{bmatrix} \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\angle Z^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e}, \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\angle Z^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e}, \\ \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\angle Z^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e}, \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\angle Z^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e}, \\ \left[\left[\left[\angle Z^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e, \left[\left[\left[\angle Z^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(4) \mathbb{S}^e = \begin{bmatrix} \left[\left[\left[\angle Z^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e, \left[\left[\left[\angle Z^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e, \\ \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\angle Z^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e}, \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\angle Z^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e}, \\ \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\angle Z^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e}, \angle^{-\infty} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\angle Z^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\infty}} \right]^e} \end{bmatrix}.$$

2.1. IVTNRFWA

Definition 2.3. Let $\mathbb{S}_i = \left\langle \left[\left[\angle Z_i^{tl}, \angle Z_i^{tu} \right], \left[\angle Z_i^{il}, \angle Z_i^{iu} \right], \left[\angle Z_i^{fl}, \angle Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right\rangle$ be the IVTNRFNs, $W = [\#_1, \#_2, \dots, \#_n]$ be the weight of \mathbb{S}_i , $\#_i \geq 0$ and $\Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \#_i = 1$. Then IVTNRFWA $[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_n] = \Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \#_i \mathbb{S}_i$.

Theorem 2.4. Let $\mathbb{S}_i = \left\langle \left[\left[\angle Z_i^{tl}, \angle Z_i^{tu} \right], \left[\angle Z_i^{il}, \angle Z_i^{iu} \right], \left[\angle Z_i^{fl}, \angle Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right\rangle$ be the IVTNRFNs. Then $IVTNRFWA[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_n]$

$$= \left[\begin{array}{cc} \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_i^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_i}, & \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_i^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_i}, \\ \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_i^{il} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_i}, & \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_i^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_i}, \\ \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_i^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}^{\#_i}, & \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}^{\#_i} \end{array} \right].$$

Proof If $n = 2$, then $IVTNRFWA[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2] = \#_1 \mathbb{S}_1 \Delta \#_2 \mathbb{S}_2$, where

$$\#_1 \mathbb{S}_1 = \left[\begin{array}{cc} \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_1}, & \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_1}, \\ \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{il} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_1}, & \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_1}, \\ \left[\left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}^{\#_1}, & \left[\left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}^{\#_1} \end{array} \right]$$

$$\#_2 \mathbb{S}_2 = \left[\begin{array}{cc} \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_2}, & \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_2}, \\ \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{il} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_2}, & \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_2}, \\ \left[\left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}^{\#_2}, & \left[\left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}^{\#_2} \end{array} \right].$$

Now, $\#_1 \mathbb{S}_1 \Delta \#_2 \mathbb{S}_2$

$$= \left[\begin{array}{cc} \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_1} + \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} \right]^{\#_2} - \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} \right]^{\#_1}, & \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_1} + \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} \right]^{\#_2} - \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} \right]^{\#_1}, \\ \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{il} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_1} + \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{il} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} \right]^{\#_2} - \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{il} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} \right]^{\#_1}, & \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}}^{\#_1} + \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} \right]^{\#_2} - \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} \right]^{\#_1}, \\ \left[\left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}^{\#_1} \cdot \left[\left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}^{\#_2}, & \left[\left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_1^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}^{\#_1} \cdot \left[\left[\left[\mathbb{F}Z_2^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha}^{\#_2} \end{array} \right]$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_1^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#1} \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_2^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#2}, \\ \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_1^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#1} \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_2^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#2}, \\ \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_1^{il} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#1} \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_2^{il} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#2}, \\ \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_1^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#1} \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_2^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#2}, \\ \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_1^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#1} \cdot \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_2^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#2}, \\ \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_1^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#1} \cdot \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_2^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Hence, IVTNRFWA $[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2]$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^2 \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i}, \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^2 \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i}, \\ \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^2 \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{il} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i}, \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^2 \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i}, \\ \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^2 \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i}, \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^2 \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i} \end{bmatrix} \cdot$$

It valid for $n \geq 3$,

Thus, IVTNRFWA $[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_l]$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i}, \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i}, \\ \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{il} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i}, \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i}, \\ \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i}, \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \angle^{-\alpha} }^{\#i} \end{bmatrix} \cdot$$

If $n = l + 1$, then IVTNRFWA $[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_l, \mathbb{S}_{l+1}]$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left[\begin{array}{l} \begin{array}{l} \Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} + \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[Z_{l+1}^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_{l+1}} \\ \sqrt{-\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} \cdot \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[Z_{l+1}^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_{l+1}}} \end{array} \\ \begin{array}{l} \Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} + \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[Z_{l+1}^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_{l+1}} \\ \sqrt{-\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} \cdot \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[Z_{l+1}^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_{l+1}}} \end{array} \\ \begin{array}{l} \Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} + \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[Z_{l+1}^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_{l+1}} \\ \sqrt{-\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} \cdot \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[Z_{l+1}^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_{l+1}}} \end{array} \\ \begin{array}{l} \Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} + \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[Z_{l+1}^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_{l+1}} \\ \sqrt{-\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} \cdot \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[Z_{l+1}^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_{l+1}}} \end{array} \\ \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} \cdot \left[\left[Z_{l+1}^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_{l+1}}, \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^l \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} \cdot \left[\left[Z_{l+1}^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_{l+1}} \end{array} \right] \\
 &= \left[\begin{array}{l} \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}}, \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}}, \\ \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}}, \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}}, \\ \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}, \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} \end{array} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.5. Let $\mathbb{S}_i = \left\langle \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl}, \downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right], \left[\downarrow Z_i^{il}, \downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right], \left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl}, \downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right\rangle$ be the IVTNRFNs. Then IVTNRFWA $[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_n] = \mathbb{S}$ (idempotency property).

Proof Since $\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl} \right] = \left[\downarrow Z^{tl} \right]$, $\left[\downarrow Z_i^{il} \right] = \left[\downarrow Z^{il} \right]$ and $\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl} \right] = \left[\downarrow Z^{fl} \right]$ and $\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right] = \left[\downarrow Z^{tu} \right]$, $\left[\downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right] = \left[\downarrow Z^{iu} \right]$ and $\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] = \left[\downarrow Z^{fu} \right]$ and $\Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \#_i = 1$. Now, IVTNRFWA $[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_n]$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left[\begin{array}{l} \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}}, \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}}, \\ \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}}, \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}}, \\ \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}, \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i} \end{array} \right] \\
 &= \left[\begin{array}{l} \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z^{tl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \#_i}}, \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z^{tu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \#_i}}, \\ \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z^{il} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \#_i}}, \sqrt{\angle^{-\alpha} \left[\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z^{iu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \#_i}}, \\ \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z^{fl} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \#_i}, \left[\left[\left[\downarrow Z^{fu} \right] \right]^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \#_i} \end{array} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left[\begin{array}{cc} \sqrt[\alpha]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil} \right] \right)}, \sqrt[\alpha]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil} \right] \right)}, \\ \sqrt[\alpha]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{il} \rceil} \rceil} \right] \right)}, \sqrt[\alpha]{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{iu} \rceil} \rceil} \right] \right)}, \\ \left[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{fl} \rceil} \rceil} \right], \left[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{fu} \rceil} \rceil} \right] \end{array} \right] \\
 &= \textcircled{S}
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.6. Let $\textcircled{S}_i = \left\langle \left[\left[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_i^{tl} \rceil} \rceil} \right], \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_i^{tu} \rceil} \rceil} \right\rangle$ be the IVTNRFNs.

Then IVTNRFWA $[\textcircled{S}_1, \textcircled{S}_2, \dots, \textcircled{S}_n]$

where $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil} = \min[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tl} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil} = \max[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tl} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{il} \rceil} \rceil} = \min[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{il} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{il} \rceil} \rceil} = \max[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{il} \rceil} \rceil}$,

$\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{fl} \rceil} \rceil} = \min[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{fl} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{fl} \rceil} \rceil} = \max[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{fl} \rceil} \rceil}$

and $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil} = \min[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tu} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil} = \max[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tu} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{iu} \rceil} \rceil} = \min[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{iu} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{iu} \rceil} \rceil} = \max[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{iu} \rceil} \rceil}$,

$\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{fu} \rceil} \rceil} = \min[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{fu} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{fu} \rceil} \rceil} = \max[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{fu} \rceil} \rceil}$ and where $1 \leq i \leq n$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, i_j$. Then,

$$\left\langle \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil}, \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil}, \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{il} \rceil} \rceil}, \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{iu} \rceil} \rceil}, \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{fl} \rceil} \rceil}, \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{fu} \rceil} \rceil} \right\rangle$$

$$\leq \text{IVTNRFWA}[\textcircled{S}_1, \textcircled{S}_2, \dots, \textcircled{S}_n]$$

$$\leq \left\langle \overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil}, \overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil}, \overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{il} \rceil} \rceil}, \overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{iu} \rceil} \rceil}, \overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{fl} \rceil} \rceil}, \overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{fu} \rceil} \rceil} \right\rangle.$$

(Boundedness property).

Proof Since, $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil} = \min[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tl} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil} = \max[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tl} \rceil} \rceil}$ and $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil} \leq \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tl} \rceil} \rceil} \leq \overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil}$ and $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil} = \min[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tu} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil} = \max[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tu} \rceil} \rceil}$ and $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil} \leq \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tu} \rceil} \rceil} \leq \overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil}$.

Now $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil}, \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sqrt[\alpha]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil} \right] \right)}^{\#_i}, \sqrt[\alpha]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil} \right] \right)}^{\#_i} \\
 &\leq \sqrt[\alpha]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tl} \rceil} \rceil} \right] \right] \right)}^{\#_i}, \sqrt[\alpha]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{tu} \rceil} \rceil} \right] \right] \right)}^{\#_i} \\
 &\leq \sqrt[\alpha]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil} \right] \right)}^{\#_i}, \sqrt[\alpha]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tu} \rceil} \rceil} \right] \right)}^{\#_i} \\
 &= \overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{tl} \rceil} \rceil}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since, $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{il} \rceil} \rceil} = \min[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{il} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{il} \rceil} \rceil} = \max[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{il} \rceil} \rceil}$ and $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{il} \rceil} \rceil} \leq \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{il} \rceil} \rceil} \leq \overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{il} \rceil} \rceil}$ and $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{iu} \rceil} \rceil} = \min[\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{iu} \rceil} \rceil}$, $\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{iu} \rceil} \rceil} = \max[\overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{iu} \rceil} \rceil}$ and $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{iu} \rceil} \rceil} \leq \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z_{ij}^{iu} \rceil} \rceil} \leq \overline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{iu} \rceil} \rceil}$.

Now, $\underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{il} \rceil} \rceil}, \underline{\lceil \lceil \lceil Z^{iu} \rceil} \rceil}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{Z}^{il}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}}, \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{Z}^{iu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}} \\
 &\leq \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{il}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}}, \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{iu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}} \\
 &\leq \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \overline{[\overline{Z}^{il}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}}, \sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \overline{[\overline{Z}^{iu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}} \\
 &= \overline{[\underline{Z}^{il}]}, \overline{[\underline{Z}^{iu}]}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since, $\underline{[\underline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} = \min[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]$, $\overline{[\overline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} = \max[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]$ and $\underline{[\underline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \leq \underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \leq \overline{[\overline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}$ and $\underline{[\underline{Z}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} = \min[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]$, $\overline{[\overline{Z}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} = \max[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]$ and $\underline{[\underline{Z}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \leq \underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \leq \overline{[\overline{Z}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}$.

We have,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{[\underline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} &= \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i}, \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \\
 &\leq \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i}, \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \\
 &\leq \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \overline{[\overline{[\underline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i}, \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \overline{[\overline{[\underline{Z}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \\
 &= \overline{[\overline{[\underline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}, \overline{[\overline{[\underline{Z}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{1}{2} \times \left[\left[\left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{Z}^{tl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}} \right]^2 - \left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{Z}^{il}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}} \right]^2 \right] \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \left[\left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}} \right]^2 - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]^2 \right] \right] \\
 &+ \left[\left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{Z}^{tu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}} \right]^2 - \left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{Z}^{iu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}} \right]^{\#_i}} \right]^2 \right] \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]^2 \right] \right] \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{2} \times \left[\left[\left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{tl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]} \right]^2 - \left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{il}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]} \right]^2 \right] + \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \left[\left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]} \right]^2 - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \underline{[\underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i}]}^{\#_i} \right]^2 \right] \right] + \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \left[\left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{tu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]} \right]^2 - \left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{iu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]} \right]^2 \right] + \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \underline{[\underline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}_{ij}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i}]}^{\#_i} \right]^2 \right] \right] \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{2} \times \left[\left[\left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \overline{[\overline{[\underline{Z}^{tl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]} \right]^2 - \left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \overline{[\overline{[\underline{Z}^{il}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]} \right]^2 \right] + \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \left[\left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \overline{[\overline{[\underline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]} \right]^2 - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \overline{[\overline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}^{fl}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i}]}^{\#_i} \right]^2 \right] \right] + \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \left[\left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \overline{[\overline{[\underline{Z}^{tu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]} \right]^2 - \left[\sqrt[\angle^{-\alpha}]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \overline{[\overline{[\underline{Z}^{iu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i} \right]} \right]^2 \right] + \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \overline{[\overline{[\underline{[\underline{Z}^{fu}]}^{\angle^{-\alpha}}]}^{\#_i}]}^{\#_i} \right]^2 \right] \right] \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle [\underline{\Delta}Z^{tl}], [\underline{\Delta}Z^{tu}], [\underline{\Delta}Z^{il}], [\underline{\Delta}Z^{iu}], [\underline{\Delta}Z^{fl}], [\underline{\Delta}Z^{fu}] \rangle \\ & \leq \overline{IVTNRFWA}[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_n] \\ & \leq \langle [\underline{\Delta}Z^{tl}], [\underline{\Delta}Z^{tu}], [\underline{\Delta}Z^{il}], [\underline{\Delta}Z^{iu}], [\underline{\Delta}Z^{fl}], [\underline{\Delta}Z^{fu}] \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.7. Let $\mathbb{S}_i = \langle [[[\underline{\Delta}Z_i^{tl}, \underline{\Delta}Z_i^{tu}], [\underline{\Delta}Z_i^{il}, \underline{\Delta}Z_i^{iu}], [\underline{\Delta}Z_i^{fl}, \underline{\Delta}Z_i^{fu}]]] \rangle$ and $W_i = \langle [[[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{tl}, \underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{tu}], [\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{il}, \underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{iu}], [\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{fl}, \underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{fu}]]] \rangle$, be the IVTNRFWAs. For any i , if there is $[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_{ij}}^{tu}]^2 \leq [\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{tu}]^2$ and $[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_{ij}}^{iu}]^2 \leq [\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{iu}]^2$ and $[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_{ij}}^{fu}]^2 \geq [\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{fu}]^2$ or $\mathbb{S}_i \leq W_i$. Prove that $IVTNRFWA[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_n] \leq IVTNRFWA[W_1, W_2, \dots, W_n]$, where $[i = 1, 2, \dots, n]; [j = 1, 2, \dots, i_j]$ (monotonicity property).

Proof For any i , $[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_{ij}}^{tl}]^2 \leq [\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{tl}]^2$.
 Therefore, $\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{tl}]]^2 \geq \alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{tl}]]^2$.
 Hence, $\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{tl}]]^2]^{\#_i} \geq \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{tl}]]^2]^{\#_i}$
 and $\sqrt[<-\infty]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{tl}]]^2]^{\#_i}} \leq \sqrt[<-\infty]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{tl}]]^2]^{\#_i}}$.
 Similarly, $[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_{ij}}^{tu}]^2 \leq [\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{tu}]^2$.
 Therefore, $\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{tu}]]^2 \geq \alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{tu}]]^2$.
 Hence, $\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{tu}]]^2]^{\#_i} \geq \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{tu}]]^2]^{\#_i}$
 and $\sqrt[<-\infty]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{tu}]]^2]^{\#_i}} \leq \sqrt[<-\infty]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{tu}]]^2]^{\#_i}}$.
 For any i , $[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_{ij}}^{il}]^{<-\infty} \leq [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{il}]]^{<-\infty}$.
 Therefore, $\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{il}]]^{<-\infty} \geq \alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{il}]]^{<-\infty}$.
 Hence, $\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{il}]]^{<-\infty}]^{\#_i} \geq \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{il}]]^{<-\infty}]^{\#_i}$.
 This implies that $\sqrt[<-\infty]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{il}]]^{<-\infty}]^{\#_i}} \leq \sqrt[<-\infty]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{il}]]^{<-\infty}]^{\#_i}}$.

Similarly, for any i , $[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_{ij}}^{iu}]^{<-\infty} \leq [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{iu}]]^{<-\infty}$.
 Therefore, $\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{iu}]]^{<-\infty} \geq \alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{iu}]]^{<-\infty}$.
 Hence, $\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{iu}]]^{<-\infty}]^{\#_i} \geq \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{iu}]]^{<-\infty}]^{\#_i}$.
 This implies that $\sqrt[<-\infty]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_i}^{iu}]]^{<-\infty}]^{\#_i}} \leq \sqrt[<-\infty]{\alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [\alpha - [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_i}^{iu}]]^{<-\infty}]^{\#_i}}$. that

For any i , $[[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_{ij}}^{fl}]]^2 \geq [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{fl}]]^2$ and $[[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_{ij}}^{fl}]]^{<-\infty} \geq [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{fl}]]^{<-\infty}$.
 Therefore, $\alpha - \frac{[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{t_{ij}}^{fl}]]^2]^{<-\infty}}{2} \leq \alpha - \frac{[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n [[\underline{\Delta}Z_{h_{ij}}^{fl}]]^2]^{<-\infty}}{2}$.
 Similarly, for any i ,

Theorem 2.12. Let $\mathbb{S}_i = \left\langle \left[\left[\left[\exists Z_i^{tl}, \exists Z_i^{tu} \right], \left[\exists Z_i^{il}, \exists Z_i^{iu} \right], \left[\exists Z_i^{fl}, \exists Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right\rangle$ be the IVTNRFNs. Then GIVTNRFWA $[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_n]$

$$= \left[\begin{array}{c} \left[\begin{array}{c} \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\left[\exists Z_i^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}}, \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\left[\exists Z_i^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}}, \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\left[\exists Z_i^{il} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}}, \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\left[\exists Z_i^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}}, \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\angle^{-\alpha} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\exists Z_i^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}}, \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\angle^{-\alpha} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\exists Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}} \end{array} \end{array} \right] \end{array} \right].$$

Proof To illustrate this, we may first show that,

$$\Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \#_i \mathbb{S}_i^{\angle^{-\alpha}} = \left[\begin{array}{c} \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\left[\exists Z_i^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}}, \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\left[\exists Z_i^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}}, \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\left[\exists Z_i^{il} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}}, \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\left[\exists Z_i^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}}, \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\angle^{-\alpha} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\exists Z_i^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}}, \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\angle^{-\alpha} \sqrt{\alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\exists Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\alpha}} \end{array} \end{array} \right].$$

$$[\Delta_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \#_i \mathbb{S}_i^e]^{1/e} = \left[\begin{array}{cc} \left[\begin{array}{c} \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}}, & \left[\begin{array}{c} \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}} \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{il} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}}, & \left[\begin{array}{c} \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}} \end{array} \right. \\ \left. \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}}, & \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^{l+1} \left[\left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}} \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right] \end{array} \right]$$

Theorem 2.13. If all $\mathbb{S}_i = \left\langle \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl}, \downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right], \left[\downarrow Z_i^{il}, \downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right], \left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl}, \downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right\rangle$ and all are equal. Then $GIVTNRFWA[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_n] = \mathbb{S}$.

2.4. Generalized IVT NRFWG (GIVT NRFWG)

Definition 2.14. Let $\mathbb{S}_i = \left\langle \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl}, \downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right], \left[\downarrow Z_i^{il}, \downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right], \left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl}, \downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right\rangle$ be the IVT-NRFNs. Then $GIVTNRFWG[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_n] = \frac{1}{\rho} \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\rho \mathbb{S}_i \right] \right] \#_i$.

Corollary 2.15. Let $\mathbb{S}_i = \left\langle \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl}, \downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right], \left[\downarrow Z_i^{il}, \downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right], \left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl}, \downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right\rangle$ be the IVTNRFNs. Then $GIVTNRFWG[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_n]$

$$= \left[\begin{array}{cc} \left[\begin{array}{c} \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}}, & \left[\begin{array}{c} \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \left[\alpha - \left[\nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}} \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{il} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}}, & \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}} \end{array} \right. \\ \left. \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}}, & \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha - \nabla_{i \rightarrow 1}^n \left[\alpha - \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right] \right] \right]^{1/\angle^{-\infty}} \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right] \end{array} \right]$$

Corollary 2.16. If all $\mathbb{S}_i = \left\langle \left[\left[\downarrow Z_i^{tl}, \downarrow Z_i^{tu} \right], \left[\downarrow Z_i^{il}, \downarrow Z_i^{iu} \right], \left[\downarrow Z_i^{fl}, \downarrow Z_i^{fu} \right] \right] \right\rangle$ are equal. Then $GIVTNRFWG[\mathbb{S}_1, \mathbb{S}_2, \dots, \mathbb{S}_n] = \mathbb{S}$.

3. Conclusion:

This work presents novel weighted operators, such as geometric and averaging operators. Boundedness, idempotency, commutativity, associativity, and monotonicity are some of the Murugan Palanikumar, Nasreen kausar and Tonguc Cagin, Trigonometric interval-valued neutrosophic set setting with reciprocal fractional function using a finite weighted method

characteristics of these operators. In order to describe the weighted vector, we looked at a number of conventional measures. A wide range of aggregation operator conditions have been investigated. Some findings have been made after a few aggregating techniques for these IVT-NRFNs have been examined.

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